

**SUTNI QURITISHNING ZAMONIY TEXNOLOGIYASI HAMDA
MAXSULOTNING XOZIRGI KUNDAGI AHMIYATI VA UNING
AVZALLIKLARI.**

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Annatsiya: Sutni quritish qurilmasini taxlil qilish jarayoni. Ushbu maqolada sut maxsulotlarni quritish jarayoni qanchalik oziq-ovqat saqlash jarayoniga kerakli ekanligi yoritib berilgan. Texnologiyalarni tanlash jarayoniga aloxida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit sozlar: Sut maxsuloti, sifat, xaroratning turg'unligi, quritish, quritish texnologiyasi, sut kukunini qo'llash, quritilgan sut, nan maxsuloti.

Annotation: Analysis Process of Milk Dryer. This article highlights how drying dairy products is essential to food preservation. Particular attention is paid to the technology selection process.

Key words: Milk product, quality, temperature stability, drying, drying technology, use of milk powder, dried milk, bread product.

Oziq-avqat maxsulotiga bo'lgan talab ortib borayotgan bir davrda ularni saqlash maxsulotni sifatini o'zgartirmagan xolatda lagistik tizimlar bilan uzoq masafaga yetkazib berish dolzarb muammoligicha qolmoqda. Maxsulotni sifatini

ozgartirmaydigan qilib saqlash uchun xol oziq-ovqatlarni quritish samarali xisoblanadi.

Quritish - bu qattiq, atala yoki suyuqlikdan bug'lanish orqali suv yoki boshqa erituvchini olib tashlashdan iborat bo'lgan massa uzatish jarayoni. Ushbu jarayon ko'pincha mahsulotni sotish yoki qadoqlashdan oldin yakuniy ishlab chiqarish bosqichi sifatida ishlatiladi. Issiqlik manbai va jarayon natijasida hosil bo'lgan bug'ni olib tashlash uchun vosita ko'pincha ishtirok etadi. Oziq-ovqat, don va farmatsevtika kabi bio-mahsulotlarda olib tashlanishi kerak bo'lgan hal qiluvchi deyarli har doim suvdur. Odatda ovqatlar suvni olib tashlash uchun issiq havo yordamida quritiladi. Samarali quritish uchun havo issiq, quruq va harakatlanuvchi bo'lishi kerak. Bu omillar o'zaro bog'liq va har bir omil to'g'ri bo'lishi muhim (masalan, sovuq harakatlanuvchi havo yoki issiq, nam harakatlanuvchi havo, ikkalasi ham qoniqarsiz). Havoning quruqligi namlik deb ataladi - namlik qancha past bo'lsa, havo shunchalik quriydi. Namlikni ifodalashning ikki yo'li mavjud; eng foydalisi havodagi suv bug'ining suv bilan to'liq to'yingan havoga nisbati. Bu nisbiy namlik (RH) deb nomlanadi. To'liq quruq havo 0% RHga ega va suv bug'i bilan to'liq to'yingan havo 100% RHga ega [1-3].

Sutni-quritish mexanizmi namlikni yo'qotishga asoslangan, buning uchun ozuqa mahsuloti ta'sir qiladigan isitiladigan atmosfera yordamida. Jarayonni uchta asosiy bosqich (atomizatsiya, tomchidan zarrachaga aylantirish va zarrachalarni yig'ish) tasvirlash mumkin. Sutni quritish jarayonida uning sifatini saqlab qalish juda muxim sanaladi. Xozirgi kunda quritilgan sut mahsulotiga bo'lgan talab ortib bormoqda [8-15].

Sut kukunini qo'llash

Quritilgan sut turli maqsadlarda ishlatilishi mumkin, masalan:

- Sut va sut mahsulotlarining rekombinatsiyasi
- Non sanoatida non hajmini oshirish va uning suv bog'lash qobiliyatini yaxshilash. Keyin non uzoq vaqt davomida yangi bo'lib qoladi
- Non va pishiriqlardagi tuxum o'rniga
- Shokolad sanoatida sutli shokolad ishlab chiqarish

- Oziq-ovqat sanoati va umumiy ovqatlanish savdosida kolbasa va har xil turdagi tayyor ovqatlar ishlab chiqarish

- Bolalar ovqatlarida
- Muzqaymoq ishlab chiqarish
- Hayvonlarning ozuqasi, buzoqlarning o'sishini tezlashtiruvchi

Qurilgan sut - sutni quruq materialga bug'lash orqali ishlab chiqarilgan sut mahsulotidir. Sutni quritishdan bir maqsad uni saqlab qolishdir; sut kukuni suyuq sutga qaraganda ancha uzoqroq saqlash muddatiga ega va namligi pastligi sababli muzlatgichda saqlash kerak emas. Yana bir maqsad - transportni tejash uchun uning asosiy hajmini kamaytirishdir. Sut kukuni va sut mahsulotlari tarkibiga quruq sut, yog'siz quruq sut, quruq ayran, quruq zardob mahsulotlari va quruq sut aralashmalari kiradi. Eksport qilinadigan ko'plab sut mahsulotlari Codex Alimentariusda belgilangan standartlarga mos keladi.

1-rasm. Sutni-quritish mexanizmining sxematik ko'rinishi. (1) Atomizatsiya. (2) Tomchidan zarrachaga o'tish. (3) Zarrachalarni yig'ishga moslashtirilgan.

Sut maxsulotini eritma atomizatorga quyiladi va suyuqlik ozuqasini atomizatorga bo'ladi

2-rasm quritish temperaturasi grafik sxemasi.

Sutning mayda tomchilarini quritish 2-rasmda keltirilgan xarorat kerakli nuqta yetganda ish yakunlanadi agar xarorat **F** nuqtaga chiqmasa arayoni davom etadi. Keyin, tomchilar namlik bug'lanishi sodir bo'lgan quritish gaz kamerasiga chiqariladi, natijada quruq zarrachalar hosil bo'ladi. Nihoyat, tegishli qurilma yordamida quritilgan zarralar quritish vositasidan ajratiladi, so'ngra tankga yig'iladi.

Xulosa hozirgi kunda sut maxsuotlarni quritish nafaqat maxsulotni sifatini saqlab qolish balki insonlarni oziq-ovqat maxsulotiga bo'lgan talabini qondirish uchun juda kata imkon beradi. Bu jarayonda zamonaviy qurilmalardan foydalanish juda muxim sanaladi. Chunki jarayon qiyin kichadi va xar bir ish sifatga kata ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

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